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Zero-thickness interface constitutive theory for concrete self-healing effects

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Abstract

A damage-plasticity constitutive theory for zero-thickness interfaces is presented aimed at predicting time-dependent self-healing phenomena in concrete. The material model is based on fracture-energy concepts and accounts for the time evolution of concrete porosity induced by the self-healing mechanism. The accuracy and soundness of the proposed interface model are demonstrated through comparative analyses of model predictions against experimental results on three point beam tests performed up to crack opening and then, up to complete failure, before and after been subjected to different exposure conditions, respectively. A wide range of experimental tests was considered in this work for both calibration and validation purposes of the proposed interface model.

Keywords: Concrete Self-Healing; Discontinuous approach; Fracture

1. Introduction

Concrete is the most widely used construction material in the world. Global cement production contributes to about 5% of annual greenhouse gas emissions (a level quite similar to those of the aviation sector), and the CO_2 released into the atmosphere, significantly affects Earth's temperature while contributes to the global warming [1]. Thus, there is an increasing demand of adopting eco-friendly design solutions in civil and structural engineering [2]. In this framework, the availability of self-healing cement-based materials capable to prevent the permeation of chemically aggressive agents, thus improving the structure durability, represents an important contribution to the achievement of eco-sustainable and greener structures [3, 4].

Nowadays, there is a consensus in the international scientific community regarding the significance and benefits of concrete self-healing features. This is based on numerous studies and contributions which allowed gaining a more clear understanding of the involved phenomena. Important conclusions of the progress made in this field are summarized in RILEM TC-221-SHC which establishes that the self-healing phenomenon in cement-based materials involves two different mechanisms: (i) the “self-closing” and (ii) the “self-healing”, respectively. The first one indicates only the closure of cracks, while the second one deals with the restoring of the mechanical properties due to healing processes. RILEM TC-221-SHC also defines the difference between “autogenic” (natural) and “autonomic” (engineered) self-closing/healing, depending on whether the crack closure or restoration of material properties is

due to either the concrete material itself or triggered by means of engineered additions [5].

In the last decades, several researches and studies were aimed at investigating the physical/chemical/mechanical behavior of cementitious materials containing “engineered” self-healing components. In this field, the use of Crystalline Additives (CAs) has been successfully explored by Sisomphon et al. [6], and Ferrara et al. [7]. These studies have shown that CAs strongly boost the mechanical restoration due to the surface crack closing phenomena while it reduces the leakage of water through cracks. Wiktor and Jonkers [8] have demonstrated and quantified the crack-healing potential of a specific two-component bio-chemical self-healing agent, embedded in clay particles which serve as particles reservoir, and partially replace the regular concrete aggregates. The capability of developing self-healing mechanism by employing polyurethane material, encapsulated by glass or ceramic cylindrical capsules to seal cracks, was shown [9]. State of the start reviews on self-healing phenomena in cement-based materials are published in the references [10, 11, 12].

Regarding constitutive theories and modeling of self-healing mechanism and its effect on the overall mechanical response behavior of concrete, all of the available proposals in the literature follow the so-called smeared-crack approach. In this sense, few constitutive models were developed so far for predicting the delayed hydration in cementitious materials and/or the carbonation process which take place due to self-healing, see [13]. Some proposals like He et al. [14] determine the amount of unhydrated cement particles in concrete specimens as a function of the water-to-cement ratio and the ce-

ment fineness which are input parameters. Recently, a constitutive model was formulated by Huang and Ye [15] aimed at simulating the hydration process in concrete using water transport and ion diffusion theories as well as thermodynamics laws. However, these models do not provide any information about the mechanical effects of self-healing. An interesting proposal is due to Lv and Chen [16] who consider a generalized reaction approach to model the hydration of cement particles. Thereby, the self-healing efficiency is quantitatively taken into account in terms of the volume fraction, the particle size distribution and the cracking modes of unhydrated cement nuclei. A coupled hydro-chemo-mechanical model is proposed in [17] to simulate the autogenous healing phenomenon of high performance concrete. Di Luzio and Cusatis [18] have formulated a Solidification-Microprestress-Microplane (SMM) model which predicts the self-healing mechanism through a suitably internal variable accounting for the cracking effects on both diffusion phenomena and also for the recovering effect due to crack-healing process [19].

This work reports the development of a zero-thickness interface model conceived in the framework of a coupled damage-plastic theory. Main objective of this proposal is the modeling of concrete cracking and failure behavior under the consideration of self-healing processes. The interface model is formulated within the general framework of the flow theory of plasticity and the continuum damage theory. The post-peak response is controlled by fully independent fracture energy-based mechanisms for both mode I and II types of failure. Based on a previous proposal by the first and second authors [20], the interface constitutive model is now extended to account for the self-healing effects on concrete stiffness, strength and post-peak response behavior under

all possible fracture modes. For this purpose a self-healing porosity parameter is formulated which governs the variation of concrete main mechanical features such as strength and stiffness through the softening and damage rule descriptions.

It is worth mentioning that classical or local strain softening models, based on the Smeared Crack Approach (SCA), lead to strong loss of objectivity regarding mesh size and orientation due to the loss of ellipticity of the involved differential equations, see a.o. [21, 22]. Thus, regularization strategies are required to suppress the ill-posedness of the differential equations [23, 24] which, at the same time, lead to unrealistic redistribution and diffusion of the failure patterns. That is why, Discrete Crack Approaches (DCAs) have become progressively attractive in solid failure mechanics. The interface model for concrete failure behavior under self-healing effects in this proposal follows the discrete crack approach and, therefore, is related to objective failure predictions regarding mesh size and orientation.

DCAs may be classified in direct ones and “on-the-fly” types. Interface model approaches [25, 26] as the one in this proposal, but also the lattice models [27, 28] and the particle model schemes [29, 30] belong to the direct procedure. Others, such as the E-FEM [31, 32], X-FEM [33, 34] and the Element-Free-Galerkin [35, 36] methods belong to the on-the-fly type of DCAs, as they introduce crack discontinuities within continuous FE domains during monotonic loading processes, once certain conditions (i.e., discontinuous bifurcation) are fulfilled. These conditions may also define the direction of the discontinuity.

After this introductory section, the proposed damage/plasticity interface

model for simulating concrete failure and post-cracking processes before and after self-healing phenomena, respectively, is formulated. The descriptions of the strength and stiffness degradation mechanisms of the interface model in the framework of the flow theory of plasticity and the isotropic damage theory are proposed in Section 3 and 4, respectively. The experimental results considered for the model calibration are reported in Section 5. The experimental campaign deals with the analysis of concrete with and without crystalline admixtures. The self-healing has been assessed by investigating the recovery of concrete mechanical properties, as determined by means of three-point bending tests performed to precrack the specimens. Then, once the specimens were exposed to different environments (water immersion and air exposure), the three-point bending tests were continued up to failure. Test data are employed as benchmark to validate the proposed interface model. Comparisons between experimental data and numerical predictions are presented and discussed in Section 6. Finally, Section 7 remarks the key results of the present research and highlights possible future research steps.

2. Coupled damage-plasticity interface model

Applying the Prandtl-Reuss additive decomposition law to the interface kinematic field,

$$\dot{\mathbf{u}} = \dot{\mathbf{u}}^{el} + \dot{\mathbf{u}}^{cr}, \quad (1)$$

with

$$\dot{\mathbf{u}}^{el} = \mathbf{C}_d^{-1} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{t}} \quad (2)$$

The coupled damage-elastoplastic constitutive equation of the interface can be expressed as

$$\dot{\mathbf{t}} = \mathbf{C}_d \cdot (\dot{\mathbf{u}} - \dot{\mathbf{u}}^{cr}) \quad (3)$$

thereby $\dot{\mathbf{u}} = [\dot{u}, \dot{v}]^t$ is the vector of relative velocities across the interface, $\dot{\mathbf{u}}^{el}$ and $\dot{\mathbf{u}}^{cr}$ are the elastic and cracking (inelastic) velocity vector components, respectively, $\dot{\mathbf{t}} = [\dot{\sigma}_N, \dot{\sigma}_T]^t$ is the interface stress rate vector and \mathbf{C}_d the elastic-damage stiffness matrix

$$\mathbf{C}_d = (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{D}) \cdot \mathbf{C} \quad (4)$$

being \mathbf{I} the second order identity matrix and \mathbf{C} the undamaged elastic matrix.

Provided the concept “effective interface stress“ is considered [37], the plastic response can be integrated independently of the damage mechanics one. Under this hypothesis Eq. (3) can be reformulated as

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\mathbf{t}} &= (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{D}) \cdot \dot{\tilde{\mathbf{t}}} \\ \dot{\tilde{\mathbf{t}}} &= \mathbf{C} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{u}}^{el} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

being $\dot{\tilde{\mathbf{t}}}$ the rate of the effective interface stress vector. Moreover, the plastic interface velocities can be computed in the effective stress space, thus independently of the damage corrector which is separately evaluated.

The tangential material operator can be finally obtained in three numerical steps:

- evaluate the elastic predictor,
- calculate the plastic corrector and
- obtain the damage corrector.

The expression of the tangential elastic-damage-plastic operator is

$$\mathbf{C}_d^{ep} = (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{D}) \cdot \mathbf{C}^{ep} \quad (6)$$

which is founded in the effective interface stress space (see Section 4).

3. Plasticity-based interface model

The constitutive interface model is now reformulated in terms of the incremental effective normal ($\dot{\tilde{\sigma}}_N$) and shear ($\dot{\tilde{\sigma}}_T$) stresses, related to the dual in-plane (\dot{u}) and out-of-plane (\dot{v}) relative velocities.

3.1. Yielding/failure surface

The yield and maximum (failure) criteria are defined by means of the following three-parameter surface (outlining the hyperbola represented in Figure 1)

$$f = \tilde{\sigma}_T^2 - (c - \tilde{\sigma}_N \tan \phi)^2 + (c - \chi \tan \phi)^2 \quad (7)$$

where the tensile strength χ (vertex of the hyperbola), the cohesion c and the frictional angle ϕ are internal parameters defining the evolution of the interface strength surface under mechanical loading.

It is worth mentioning that Eq. (7) outlines two main failure modes:

- *Mode I*: direct tensile fracture, which is obtained when the stress state reaches the intersection between the strength surface and the normal effective stress axis (i.e., the horizontal axis).
- *Mode II*: direct shear fracture under effective confinement. This failure mode is reached when the stress state reaches the asymptotic zone of the maximum strength surface of the interface.

3.2. Plastic flow rule

The vector of relative plastic displacement rates, according to a non-associated flow rule, can be defined as

$$\dot{\mathbf{u}}^{cr} = \dot{\lambda} \mathbf{m} \quad (8)$$

where $\dot{\lambda}$ is the non-negative plastic multiplier which derives from the classical Kuhn-Tucker loading/unloading and consistency conditions

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\lambda} \geq 0, \quad f \leq 0, \quad \dot{\lambda} f = 0 & \quad \text{Kuhn - Tucker} \\ \dot{f} = 0 & \quad \text{Consistency} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where $f = f[\tilde{\sigma}_N, \tilde{\sigma}_T]$ is the yield condition of the interface while \mathbf{m} the vector controlling the direction of the fracture displacements by means of a non-associated flow rule

$$\mathbf{m} = \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{n} \quad (10)$$

being

$$\mathbf{n} = \frac{\partial f}{\partial \tilde{\mathbf{t}}} = \left[\frac{\partial f}{\partial \tilde{\sigma}_N}, \frac{\partial f}{\partial \tilde{\sigma}_T} \right]^t = [\mathbf{2} \tan \phi (\mathbf{c} - \tilde{\sigma}_N \tan \phi), \mathbf{2} \tilde{\sigma}_T]^t \quad (11)$$

the direction of the associated plastic flow.

The transformation matrix \mathbf{A} in Eq. (10) is

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{cases} \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\tan \beta}{\tan \phi} & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} & \text{if } \tilde{\sigma}_N \geq 0 \\ \begin{pmatrix} \left[1 - \frac{|\tilde{\sigma}_N|}{\tilde{\sigma}_{dil}}\right] \frac{\tan \beta}{\tan \phi} & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} & \text{if } -\tilde{\sigma}_{dil} \leq \tilde{\sigma}_N < 0 \\ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} & \text{if } \tilde{\sigma}_N < -\tilde{\sigma}_{dil} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

where $\tan \beta$ is the dilation angle of the plastic potential (Figure 1): with $0 \leq \tan \beta \leq \tan \phi$. Thereby, the parameter $\tilde{\sigma}_{dil}$ represents the normal effective stress at which the dilatancy vanishes [38].

3.3. Softening/re-hydration evolution law

In this proposal a multiplicative decomposition is considered for the internal variables controlling the evolution of the interface yield surface in post-peak regime. This decomposition involves two components describing the post-peak response due to the mechanical and the hydraulic effects, as

$$p_i = g_1 (S[\xi_{p_i}]) g_2 (\text{SH}[\psi]) p_{0i} \quad (13)$$

where p_i alternatively represents χ , c and $\tan \phi$ of Eq. (7) while ξ_{p_i} accounts for the effect of the ratio between the spent fracture work against the available energies (in mode I or II) and ψ is the self-healing porosity factor.

Eq. (13) defines the typical evolution law of the internal parameters from their maximum (or initial) values, $p_i = p_{0i}$, to the residual ones. In this sense, the following scaling functions are proposed for taking into account fracture processes caused by mechanical effects

$$g_1 (S[\xi_{p_i}]) = \left(1 - (1 - r_{p_i}) S[\xi_{p_i}] \right), \quad (14)$$

and the restoration of internal proprieties due to self-healing

$$g_2 (\text{SH}[\psi]) = (\text{SH}[\psi]) sh, \quad (15)$$

where r_{p_i} measures the residual amounts of the internal parameters under mechanical loadings while sh a self-healing scalar parameter.

3.3.1. Softening due to mechanical fracture

The scaling function $S[\xi_{p_i}]$ in Eqs. (13) and (14) is defined by means of the following relationship

$$S[\xi_{p_i}] = \frac{e^{-\alpha_{p_i}} \xi_{p_i}}{1 + (e^{-\alpha_{p_i}} - 1) \xi_{p_i}} \quad (16)$$

whereby the parameter α_{p_i} controls the decay form of the internal parameter, while the non-dimensional variable ξ_{p_i} accounts for the influence on $S[\xi_{p_i}]$ of the ratio between the fracture work (currently spent) and the available fracture energy in mode I or II (G_f^I or G_f^{IIa}) according to the following C^1 continuity function proposed by [39]

$$\xi_\chi = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2} \left[1 - \cos \left(\frac{\pi W_{cr}}{G_f^I} \right) \right] & \text{if } W_{cr} \leq G_f^I \\ 1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, \quad (17)$$

$$\xi_c = \xi_{\tan \phi} = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2} \left[1 - \cos \left(\frac{\pi W_{cr}}{G_f^{IIa}} \right) \right] & \text{if } W_{cr} \leq G_f^{IIa} \\ 1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}. \quad (18)$$

The fracture work spent, W_{cr} , spent during an opening-sliding process, controls the evolutions of the material parameters χ , c and $\tan \phi$ in softening regime of the interface response. Particularly, the variable W_{cr} defines the necessary amount of released energy to open a single crack in tensile and/or shear fracture mode due to normal $\tilde{\sigma}_N$ and/or tangential $\tilde{\sigma}_T$ effective stresses.

Therefore, the rate of the fracture work \dot{W}_{cr} spent, during a generic fracture process, is defined as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{W}_{cr} &= \tilde{\sigma}_N \cdot \dot{u}^{cr} + \tilde{\sigma}_T \cdot \dot{v}^{cr}, \quad \text{if } \tilde{\sigma}_N \geq 0, \\ \dot{W}_{cr} &= [\tilde{\sigma}_T - |\tilde{\sigma}_N| \tan(\phi)] \cdot \dot{v}^{cr}, \quad \text{if } \tilde{\sigma}_N < 0. \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

Finally, the total dissipated work is obtained by integrating the fracture work increments during the entire fracture process.

3.3.2. Softening due to self-healing porosity

The g_2 (SH[ψ]) function in Eq. (13) describes the post-peak response of the interface due to the self-healing phenomenon through the so-called self-healing porosity. This parameter defines the evolution of the concrete open-porosity during self-healing processes as outlined in Eq. (15), being

$$\text{SH}[\psi] = \frac{e^{-\varsigma_{p_i} \psi}}{1 + (e^{-\varsigma_{p_i}} - 1)\psi} \quad (20)$$

where ς_{p_i} controls the decay forms of the porosity-based post-peak function SH[ψ] (Figure 2), while ψ is the self-healing porosity factor which is defined as follows

$$\psi = \frac{\phi_c - \phi_f}{\phi_0 - \phi_f} \quad \phi_c \in [\phi_0, \phi_f] \quad (21)$$

being ϕ_c the current open porosity of the interface plane which varies during the re-hydration and self-healing process from its initial value ϕ_0 up to the maximum or final one ϕ_f .

4. Isotropic damage formulation

In this study, a scalar-type approach is employed to describe the isotropic damage as proposed through Eqs. (4, 5 and 6).

Relevant researches on this topic assumed an exponential form of the damage variable as function of the equivalent plastic tensile strain [40, 41, 42, 43]. In this interface model proposal two independent scalar damages are considered, d^I and d^{IIa} , which vary into the range $[0, 1]$. Thereby, $d^{I/IIa} =$

0 corresponds to the undamaged interface, while $d^{I/IIa} = 1$ to the fully damaged one.

The damage evolution is described by means of the following unified rule based on the fracture work [44]

$$d^{I/IIa} = \frac{e^{-\beta_d} \left(\frac{W_{cr}}{G_f^{I/IIa}} \right)^{\alpha_d}}{1 + (e^{-\beta_d} - 1) \left(\frac{W_{cr}}{G_f^{I/IIa}} \right)^{\alpha_d}} \quad (22)$$

whereby the parameters $\alpha_d \geq 0$ and β_d control the decay form of the damage induced by fracture, as shown in Figures 3 and 4.

Finally, Eq. (4) expands into

$$\mathbf{C}_d = \begin{pmatrix} 1 - d^I & 0 \\ 0 & 1 - d^{IIa} \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} k_N & 0 \\ 0 & k_T \end{pmatrix} \quad (23)$$

while the tangential elastic-damage-plastic operator of Eq. (6) can be written as

$$\mathbf{C}_d^{ep} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 - d^I & 0 \\ 0 & 1 - d^{IIa} \end{pmatrix} \cdot \left(\mathbf{C} - \frac{\mathbf{C} \cdot \mathbf{m} \otimes \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{C}}{H + \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{C} \cdot \mathbf{m}} \right) \quad (24)$$

being H the so-called softening parameter [20].

5. Outline of the experimental test results

The composition of the investigated concrete mixtures is listed in Table 1. Both autogenous healing and engineered one, through the use of crystalline admixtures, have been studied.

The employed crystalline admixture consists of a blend of cement, sand and microsilica; SEM magnified particles are shown in Figures 5a-b: they

have irregular shape and size in the range of about $1 - 20 \mu m$ and their morphology is similar to that of cement grains. EDS analysis confirmed the presence of calcium, oxygen, silicon, magnesium, aluminum and potassium (Figure 5c), once again comparably to ordinary Portland cement, except for the slightly higher sulfur peak.

A three-stage dedicated experimental methodology has been developed for the characterization of self-healing through the quantification of its effects on the recovery of mechanical properties:

- Pre-cracking the specimens, up to crack-opening thresholds, under 3-point-bending test schemes; geometry of the specimens and pre-cracking thresholds, were tailored to the material. Geometry of specimens and test set-ups are shown in Figure 6;
- Exposing the specimens to different environments and for different times;
- Testing the specimens, after conditioning, up to failure according to the same set-up employed for the pre-cracking.

More specifically, several concrete slabs ($1000 \text{ mm long} \times 500 \text{ mm wide} \times 50 \text{ mm thick}$) were cast with and without additives. After three days curing in fog room at $20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ temperature, 95 % Relative Humidity (RH) and under wet towels, such slabs were cut into $500 \text{ mm} \times 100 \text{ mm} \times 50 \text{ mm}$ prismatic specimens (Figure 6a). Beam specimens were then cured in the same fog room for a time period between 35 and 42 days. In order to evaluate the concrete self-healing capacity and its effect on the recovery of mechanical properties, after the aforementioned curing period, the beam specimens were

pre-cracked up to the residual crack opening of $250 \mu m$. The three-point beam test (3PB) set-up outlined in Figure 6b was followed using the Crack Opening Displacement (COD) at mid-span as a control variable. All the specimens were then subjected to different controlled exposure conditions: (i) immersion in water at constant temperature, equal to $20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, or (ii) exposure to air (while daily recording minimum and maximum temperature and average RH [7]). Four times of exposure were considered for both underwater and air conditioning: i.e., 1, 2, 6 and 12 months. Finally, at the end of the scheduled exposure times, the 3pb tests were performed again, on each specimen, until its complete failure.

Table 2 provides a synopsis of the experimental program as a whole. Comparative analysis of pre-cracking and post-conditioning experimental results, in terms of nominal bending stress vs. COD curves, allows to assess the recovery of residual strength, stiffness and, in case, ductility, as a proof of the occurred crack healing, complemented by optical microscopy observation of the partially or even totally sealed cracks.

In Figures 7-8-9-10, experimental results in terms of vertical load vs. COD curves are shown. Images of healed cracks (highlighted in Figure 11) support the aforementioned statements. Moreover, pictures from SEM analysis (see Figure 12) highlight on crack surfaces the presence healing products on crack surfaces, whose composition resembles that of cement hydration products and is coherent with the one of the additive employed as a self-healing catalyst.

It is worth mentioning that for the sake of brevity the complete description and discussion of the experimental programme is omitted in this work. However deep and detailed information about it are available in the paper

published by two of the Authors (see [7]).

6. Validation of the model and numerical predictions

This section aims at validating the proposed interface model by performing and comparing numerical examples against the experimental results outlined in the previous section.

The numerical results try to simulate the specimens tested under three-point bending. Particularly, in order to evaluate the self-healing capacity of concrete at numerical standpoint and its effects on the recovery of the mechanical properties, three numerical steps were considered into the FEM analyses: (i) in the first one, the beam specimen was pre-cracked up to a certain level of COD (namely residual crack opening); (ii) the second step which is characterized by a considered elapsed time (exposure time) and finally (iii) the ultimate step which allows to evaluate the total failure of the specimen and with which it can be evaluate the self-healing capacity of concrete.

For the calibration purpose of the numerical examples, four families (having different exposure and/or mixture types of concrete) were considered as follows:

- AEWA: Air Exposure Without crystalline Admixture;
- AECA: Air Exposure with Crystalline Admixture;
- WEWA: Water Conditioning Without crystalline Admixture;
- WECA: Water Conditioning with Crystalline Admixture.

Finite element analyses adopt the geometry shown in Figure 13 considering $100 \times 50 \times 450 \text{ mm}^3$ concrete specimens according to [7]. Figure 14 proposes the FE discretization employed in the present analysis. Plane stress hypothesis and displacement-based control are assumed. Four-node iso-parametric elements, equipped with a linear elastic model, have been adopted in the FE mesh, while all non-linearities are concentrated within zero-thickness interfaces defined throughout the adjacent edges of the finite elements in the cracked zone of the beam (Figure 14). Particularly, non-linear porosity and fracture/damage-based interface rules were introduced in those interface elements according to the formulation outlined in Sections 2-3-4.

The key geometric and material properties of the numerical examples were chosen according to the experimental evidences [7]. Based on the calibration procedure, the elastic modulus and Poisson's ratio of concrete (continuous FEs) was $E_c = 21.70 \text{ GPa}$ and $\nu = 0.17$ for all mixtures, respectively. Then, the mechanical parameters of the interface model are here listed: $k_N = 500 \text{ MPa/mm}$, $k_T = 200 \text{ MPa/mm}$, $\tan \phi_0 = 0.6$, $\tan \beta = 0.3$, $r_{\tan \phi} = 0.67$, $\sigma_{dil} = 10 \text{ MPa}$, for all mixtures. Finally, Table 3 figures out the calibrated parameters for the fracture-based, self-healing and damage functions of the interface model.

Notice that as a result of the calibration procedure, ξ_{p_i} is negative in every considered test and conditioning case. This is actually expected as it is related to the reduction of the rate of hydration (or re-hydration) under increasing exposure/conditioning time frame. As a matter of fact, high values of ψ mainly represent small exposure/conditioning time frame (and vice versa small ψ values account for elevated exposure/conditioning time

frames). This behavior, which always occurs in all hydration process of cementitious materials [45, 46, 47], takes place also in re-hydration self-healing phenomena.

After the calibration procedure, Figures 15-16-17-18-(a) show the force-deflection curves against the corresponding experimental results. All those tests refer to 12-months conditioning type. It can be observed that the post-cracking response is very well captured through the considered discontinuous approach based on non-linear interfaces. Furthermore, the comparison between the experimental and numerical results in terms of the load vs. crack opening displacement (COD) highlights as the model is able to predict both the softening behavior in the pre-cracking stage and the self-healing recovery of the load bearing capacity after the conditioning with respect to the unloading value at which the value decayed in the pre-cracking stage.

On the other hand, Figures 15-16-17-18-(b) reproduce the comparisons in terms of a proposed “Index of load Recovery” (IR) between the numerical simulations against the experimental data for all conditioning types and times for both (with and without crystalline admixtures) the analyzed mixtures. IR was defined as follows

$$IR = \frac{f_{R,\max\text{ POST-CONDITIONING}} - f_{R,\text{unloading PRE-CRACK}}}{f_L} \quad (25)$$

where $f_L = \frac{3P_L l}{2bh^2}$, being P_L the maximum flexural load; b , h and l are the width, height and length of the beam, respectively. $f_{R,\max\text{ POST-CONDITIONING}}$ and $f_{R,\text{unloading PRE-CRACK}}$ represent the post-cracking flexural stresses (evaluated similarly to f_L) related to the $P_{R,\max\text{ POST-CONDITIONING}}$ and $P_{R,\text{unloading PRE-CRACK}}$ loads, respectively. Moreover, $P_{R,\max\text{ POST-CONDITIONING}}$ represents the flexural load corresponding to the maximum COD value of the pre-cracking

stage while $P_{R,unloading\ PRE-CRACK}$ is the maximum flexural load of the post-treatment stage.

Finally, the recovery predictions of the flexural loads are well reproduced by means of the numerical model as indicated throughout Figures 15-16-17-18-(b), especially for the cases of water conditioning where the scatter of the experimental results is less pronounced.

7. Conclusions

This paper addressed the formulation of a fracture/damage and porosity-based interface model for analyzing post-peak behavior of cementitious composites due to the combined action of mechanical loading and self-healing phenomenon. The model is calibrated with experimental results involving self-healing processes and, then, the predictive capabilities of the interface formulation is evaluated with further experimental test results.

Based on the features of the proposed interface model and the obtained results, following conclusions can be drawn out:

- The proposed formulation explicitly model the porosity evolutions due to self-healing.
- Novel concept and formulations were introduced to account for pore closure and evolution due to self-healing phenomenon, and to describe the resulting evolution of concrete post-peak strength.
- Numerical analyses demonstrated the predictive capabilities of the constitutive model in terms of the most relevant aspects of the mechanical behavior of concrete after crack closure due to self-healing processes

and under consideration of several exposure conditions and different concrete mixtures.

Further developments are currently ongoing for better understanding other relevant aspects, such as the prediction and modeling of the moisture diffusion in concrete which could directly influence the re-hydration effect of cementitious materials. As a matter of fact, several parameters based on physical arguments which are involved in the proposed formulation such as porosity variables, self-healing products and re-hydration phenomena could be directly related to diffusion and reaction processes and still require more investigations. As a matter of principle, this is a straightforward evolution of the model presented in this paper which was only limited to the study of the mechanical and fracture mechanisms effects due self-healing phenomena.

Finally, it is nowadays widely accepted that complex multiphysical processes in composite materials like concrete such as self-healing effects may be more accurately modeled through multiscale analyzes based on homogenization procedures as well as through full 3D formulations. The interface model proposed in this paper can be certainly employed in multiscale studies whereby some of the involved physical or ~~cinematic~~ **kinematic** variables could be evaluated through homogenization procedures ~~in the framework of the Hill-Mandel postulate~~. Also, the proposed interface model for self-healing processes in concrete can be extended for 3D analysis and computational simulations. Precisely, the extension to a 3D interface model formulation represents a very interesting item for future researches associated to self-healing computational modeling.

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Table 1: Mix design of investigated cement-based materials.

Constituents	Dosage (kg/m ³)	
	Ref.	Ref.
Cement CEM II 42.5 A/L	300	300
Crystalline admixture	=	3
Water	180	180
	w/c = 0.6	
Superplasticizer	3	3
NW fine aggregate 0-4 mm	1080	1077
NW coarse aggregate 4-16 mm	880	880

Table 2: Experimental programme synopsis.

	Concrete with Crystalline admixture	Concrete without Crystalline admixture
<i>Crack opening</i>	250 μ m	
<i>Exposure condition</i>		
Water immersion	1,2,6,12	
Air exposure	1,2,6,12	

Table 3: Fracture-based, self-healing and damage parameters employed in the numerical analyses.

Test Label	Fracture-based interface				Porosity-based scaling rule			Damage parameters	
	χ_o [MPa]	c_o [MPa]	G_f^I [N/mm]	G_f^{IIa} [N/mm]	α_χ	ζ_{pi}	sh	α_d	β_d
AEWA	1.90	4.20	0.10	1.00	0.25	-0.73	7.24%	4.0	-4.0
AECA	2.96	6.37	0.17	1.70	1.00	-0.85	4.94%	4.0	-3.5
WEWA	2.18	4.69	0.13	1.30	1.00	-0.04	5.07%	4.0	-4.0
WECA	1.95	4.20	0.18	1.80	1.00	-1.50	5.79%	4.0	-4.0

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WITH ADDITIVE – AIR CONDITIONING

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